

NFDI4Earth

NFDI4Earth White Paper

NFDI4Earth Cooperation – re3data

Task Area 3 - 2Interoperate

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Executive summary

In this document the cooperation between re3data (Registry of Research Data Repositories) and the NFDI4Earth is described. The cooperation covers strategies to update metadata entries, and register missing repositories from the ESS (Earth System Science) field. Further, the aim is to identify additional useful metadata fields, and crosslink activities, such as workshops and newsletters.

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1 Introduction

For the NFDI4Earth, re3data¹ (Registry of Research Data Repositories) plays an important role. re3data is a global registry that lists and provides detailed information about research data repositories. It is designed to help researchers, funding bodies, publishers, and institutions to find appropriate repositories to store and share research data. One of the key features of re3data is that it contains information about repositories across all academic disciplines, including life sciences, social sciences, humanities, and engineering in a comprehensive listing. Each repository is described with detailed metadata. To achieve this, re3data uses a standardized set of metadata that includes details like the DFG subject area², content types, access policies, licensing, and the repository certification status. It provides a comprehensive filter functionality so that users can search and filter repositories, among many others criteria, by discipline, country, type of data, or open access. Further, re3data provides information, whether a repository is certified by e.g. the CoreTrustSeal or ISO metadata standards, such as the ISO 19115 standard, which ensures data quality and sustainability. Assigning DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers) to repositories increases interoperability, which not only encourages adherence to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles, but also helps repository providers to improve visibility of their repositories.

2 Motivation

One of the main tasks of the NFDI4Earth is to collect all existing and new services in a service catalogue. These services have to be described in detail, e.g., in regard to openness, used standards, and certification, and have to be continuously collected and updated in the NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub³. Additionally, the aim is to gather and ingest information about services in a (semi)automatic way.

As part of a project funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) to develop a global registry of research data repositories, re3data exists since 2012, and is collecting this kind of information about repositories since then. re3data uses persistent identifiers to reference the repositories it lists. Each repository in re3data is assigned a DOI, which ensures that the repository information is easily citable and accessible over time. This persistent identifier allows to reliably reference the repository and its details, contributing to the long-term stability and accessibility of research data infrastructures. This also allows the NFDI4Earth to harvest

¹ <https://www.re3data.org/>

² <https://www.dfg.de/en/research-funding/proposal-funding-process/interdisciplinarity/subject-area-structure>

³ [https://knowledgehub.nfdi4earth.de/%5D\(https://knowledgehub.nfdi4earth.de/](https://knowledgehub.nfdi4earth.de/%5D(https://knowledgehub.nfdi4earth.de/)

this existing information. The NFDI4Earth benefits from the long-term experience and well-established collection of re3data, and harvests repository metadata via the Knowledge Hub, using the re3data repository identifier.

However, there are also some challenges, which need to be overcome.

- a) The metadata is generic and ESS specific metadata is missing
- b) Useful additional metadata fields have to be identified
- c) Metadata has to be kept up to date on a regular basis
- d) Outdated and not existing repositories have to be marked accordingly
- e) Not all ESS relevant repositories are registered with re3data

3 NFDI4Earth and re3data cooperation

As re3data and the NFDI4Earth face the same challenges regarding updating entries, registering new repositories, dealing with outdated entries, it was obvious that a **cooperation** benefits both parties. The addition of useful new metadata fields is of interest to the NFDI4Earth and re3data. However, re3data depicts a generic collection of repositories on an international basis, and has therefore a different emphasis on appropriate additional metadata fields, while the NFDI4Earth has an interest in adding ESS specific metadata fields. Yet, both parties agreed in their collaboration that it is also feasible to develop service metadata schemas that specifically meet the ESS community's requirements.

4 Results

In context of this cooperation the NFDI4Earth has identified missing or incorrect metadata fields, and outdated repositories and passed the information on to re3data. In this way, re3data and the NFDI4Earth have established a very successful and timely exchange of update information.

4.1 Metadata

Regarding metadata of repositories, we have achieved the following results so far:

- 16 repository entries related to ESS were updated in 2024 regarding the entries for persistent identifiers for research organizations, the ROR ID⁴

⁴ <https://ror.org/about/>

- 4 repository entries were identified and reported to re3data in 2024 for updating:
 - re3data.org/repository/r3d100012343
 - re3data.org/repository/r3d100013674
 - re3data.org/repository/r3d100011650
 - re3data.org/repository/r3d100013812
- in the registration process the metadata entry “enhanced publication” is necessary⁵ yet, it was reported that the meaning is not quite clear. With this feedback, re3data explained this field in more detail.

4.2 Suggesting Repositories to re3data

In the beginning of the NFDI4Earth project, metadata of repositories was collected manually as a NFDI4Earth service catalogue⁶. Some of these repositories are not yet registered with re3data. As described already earlier, the NFDI4Earth harvests the metadata information from re3data, and plans to keep the metadata fields updated via re3data, therefore there is a keen interest that the remaining repositories also register with re3data.

Before a repository can be submitted to re3data, the eligibility of the repository has to be ensured. Some of these basic criteria for inclusion are that the repository offers open access to research data or provide data access services, it should be a sustained platform (preferably long-term), primarily focus on research data (i.e., data that supports scientific or scholarly research), and clearly describe its terms of use and data policies.

In the next step some information about the repository has to be gathered, such as the repository name and description, the URL of the repository, the DFG subject areas⁷ or disciplines covered by the repository, the types of data accepted, the access and licensing policies, the persistent identifiers (PIDs) used (e.g., DOI, Handle), and certifications or standards the repository adheres to (if applicable)⁸.

The repository has to be suggested to re3data via the re3data online suggest form⁹. In an

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.48440/re3.014>

⁶ Müller, C. M., & Frickenhaus, S. (2023). NFDI4Earth Service Catalogue and Gap Analysis (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8344438>

⁷ <https://www.dfg.de/en/research-funding/proposal-funding-process/interdisciplinarity/subject-area-structure>

⁸ Strecker, D., Axtmann, A., Bertelmann, R., Cousijn, H., Elger, K., Ferguson, L. M., Fichtmüller, D., Jones, C., Lindenmann, I., Neidiger, C., Nguyen, T. B., Pal, J. K., Pampel, H., Petras, V., Schnepf, E., Semrau, A., Ulrich, R., Upmeier, A., Vierkant, P., Wang, H., Weickert, G., Weisweiler, N. L., Williams, S. C., Witt, M., Wright, S. J. (2023): Metadata Schema for the Description of Research Data Repositories: version 4.0, re3data, 33 p. <https://doi.org/10.48440/re3.014>

⁹ <https://www.re3data.org/suggest>

editorial process the filled in information is then reviewed and the repository provider informed about acceptance.

So far, the NFDI4Earth was successful in suggesting the “ATTO data portal”, the “Geodatenkatalog”, and “Helmholtz Coastal Data Center (HCDC)” to re3data. Not all the suggested repositories were willing to go through this process. Reasons were that technical features were not up-to-date but will be changed in the near future, or the integration will take place at a later stage. Tab. 1 shows a list of examples of repositories, which to the NFDI4Earth appeared suitable to be suggested for registration with re3data. Only in discussions with the providers was it finally possible to clarify whether this was actually the case.

Table 1: Mapping the NFDI4Earth repository landscape, some examples of repositories that appear suitable for registration with re3data are shown

Repository	URL	Registered with re3data in 2024
ATTO – Amazon Tall Tower Observatory data portal	https://www.attodata.org/home/Start	http://doi.org/10.17616/R31NJNLK
BGR-Geoportal	https://geoportal.bgr.de/mapapps/resources/apps/geoportal/index.html	-
Copernicus Data and Exploitation Platform - Germany (CODE-DE)	https://code-de.org/de/	-
Earth Data Portal	https://earth-data.de/	-
EOWEB GeoPortal	https://eoweb.dlr.de/egp/	-
Geodatenkatalog (Geoportal)	https://geoportal.de/	http://doi.org/10.17616/R31NJNKT
GEOMAR (Near-) Realtime-Data from Glider and Moorings	https://data.geomar.de/realtime/html/index.html	-
Helmholtz Coastal Data Center (HCDC)	http://doi.org/10.17616/R31NJNFD	https://hcdc.hereon.de/datasearch/
Marine Dateninfrastruktur Deutschland (MDI-DE)	https://www.mdi-de.org/mdi-de/	-
Oceanographic Data Center (DOD)	https://www.bsh.de/EN/DATA/Climate-and-Sea/Oceanographic/_Data/_Center/oceanographic/_data/_center/_node.html	At a later stage

In the process of suggesting repositories, a lot of discussions with the providers took place, and in this context awareness for this process has been sharpened. The process is ongoing and not yet finished.

4.3 Meetings with re3data

Several meetings between the NFDI4Earth and the re3data editorial team took place: the first one in November 2023 and the second in February 2024. In these meetings an update strategy, and the development of additional metadata fields was discussed. Further it is planned to crosslink activities, such as newsletters, and organize joint workshops. In this sense a memorandum of understanding was formulated and signed in spring 2024.

5 Outlook

In the course of the cooperation a lot of progress has been achieved. Updating and adding to the metadata is an ongoing process. Further repositories have to be encouraged to register with re3data, as soon as suitability is confirmed. This process can be further supported with provider workshops.